

Conditional Variational Autoencoder for Causal Inference in Healthcare

September 2023

AUTHOR(S):

Sara Zoccheddu

CERN EP-LBD

SUPERVISOR(S):

Nicola Serra (CERN / UZH)

Olivia Jullian Parra (CERN)

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my gratitude to my supervisor, Nicola Serra, for giving me the chance to work on a project that aligns with my future aspirations. A special thanks goes to Olivia, both a supervisor and a project mate, constant source of support and knowledge. Her guidance has been invaluable. And to my other teammates, Shrija, Max, and Thomas, thank you for the collaboration and the memorable moments. It has been an honor to collaborate with such an outstanding group.

Abstract

In recent times, there has been a significant increase in the literature dedicated to the application of Machine Learning in healthcare. Yet, the translation of this research into routine clinical care is progressing more gradually. This lag can be attributed both to the black-box nature of machine learning techniques and to instances where the improvements over traditional approaches, while statistically notable, lack clinical significance. Multimorbidity is one domain where the conventional techniques could fall short.

This research project is centered on a new approach that leverages generative models to predict patient paths in multimorbidity, integrating expert knowledge through causal inference. This method enhances both interpretability and sensitivity of the models. The primary interest of this particular project lies in exploiting Conditional Variational Autoencoders. The approach of this report aims to validate the CVAE's effectiveness on real-world data scenarios and compare the results with the ones of more traditional methods. Finally, we hope to establish a comprehensive understanding of CVAE's potential in healthcare.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	05
<hr/>	
2. Machine Learning for Causal Inference in Multimorbidity	06
<hr/>	
3. Conditional Variational Autoencoder (CVAE)	09
<hr/>	
4. The International Stroke Trial (IST) dataset	11
<hr/>	
5. Quality assurance and informed study	14
<hr/>	
6. Framework: Generative Models in Artificial Intelligence	17
<hr/>	
7. Conclusions	18
<hr/>	
8. References	18

1. Introduction

As the complexity of the global health landscape grows, it arises an imperative need to evolve our analytical tools and methodologies. The phenomenon of multimorbidity, which refers to the simultaneous existence of two or more chronic conditions in an individual, presents unique challenges to healthcare professionals and researchers. In order to develop effective treatment strategies and predict outcomes, we need a sophisticated understanding of the underlying causal relationships. It's here that machine learning can help us in managing complex datasets and extracting meaningful insights.

This report focuses on studying how generative models, in particular Conditional Variational Autoencoders (CVAEs), can help us in understanding causal inference.

We will apply the CVAE model to a real-world data scenario such as the International Stroke Trial (IST) dataset. The IST, conducted from 1991 to 1996, offers a rich repository of data regarding patient outcomes linked to various treatments for acute ischemic stroke. Our goal is to ascertain if a CVAE can reconstruct this data, predict factual and counterfactual outcomes, and offer insights comparable to those derived from Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs).

RCTs, while extremely useful, often demand a large cohort of participants, making them challenging and sometimes infeasible. Can a machine learning model, like CVAE, offer a viable alternative? Furthermore, can such models help us to better understand multimorbidity treatments and outcomes, where traditional methods might fall short?

Combining machine learning's computational capability with clinical expertise has the potential to reshape the healthcare research, producing more detailed and practicable insights. This report digs into these prospects, exploring the capabilities and implications of applying Conditional VAEs in the healthcare domain.

2. Machine Learning for Causal Inference in Multimorbidity

What is causal inference? **Causal inference** aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between two or more variables.

We can model causality applied to a simple healthcare context with the following Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG):

Figure 1. Conceptual causal model.

- Observational Confounders (X):**
 These are variables that could potentially influence both the treatment assignment and the outcome. They can include, for instance, patient's age, BMI, blood pressure, and other previous treatments. These are all factors that might influence a physician's decision to prescribe a treatment and might also influence the outcome.
- Treatment (t):**
 This is a binary variable indicating whether a treatment (e.g., aspirin) is administered or not. We have that $t=1$ if the treatment was taken and $t=0$ if not.
- Medical Outcome (y):**
 This is the result we are interested in. It indicates the medical outcome, such as whether the patient died, did not recover, or recovered after receiving the treatment.

In this model, we are conditioning y on X . The goal in causal inference is often to compare the outcomes between treated and untreated individuals as if the treatment were randomized. In observational data, treatment is not randomized and might be influenced by confounders (X). To account for these confounders, we condition on them. This means we adjust for these variables in our analysis to try and isolate the effect of the treatment on the outcome.

In particular, the expression $p(y | X, t=0 \text{ or } t=1)$ represents the probability of observing a particular outcome y given the confounders X and whether the treatment t was taken or not. This conditional probability aims to estimate the causal effect of the treatment on the outcome, adjusting for the confounders X .

Causal inference and multimorbidity

Causal inference can be particularly useful in the context of multimorbidity. **Multimorbidity** is defined as the coexistence of two or more chronic conditions in the same individuals.

Patients with multimorbidity often undergo multiple treatments simultaneously. Understanding the causal relationships between various treatments and outcomes can guide more effective and individualized care strategies. It is vital to ensure patients are receiving optimal care; without understanding causality, there's a risk of attributing positive or negative outcomes to the wrong treatment.

However, understanding causal inference can be challenging because there might be hidden confounders that influence both the predictor and the outcome, creating a false impression of a direct causal relationship. For instance, sicker patients might receive more aggressive treatments, making it look like the treatment is harmful when, in reality, the severity of the illness is driving the worse outcome. Causal inference techniques can help adjust for this confounding factor.

In essence, in the complex world of multimorbidity, where patients have intertwined health conditions and treatments, understanding the true causal relationships between interventions and outcomes is essential. It informs better clinical decisions, ensures optimal patient outcomes, and leads to more efficient use of healthcare resources.

To address these challenges, various statistical and experimental methods, such as randomized controlled trials (RCTs), have been developed.

Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) are often considered the "gold standard" for establishing causality in clinical research. In a Randomized Controlled Trial, participants are randomly assigned to either a treatment group, which receives the treatment, or a control group, which does not receive the treatment. This randomization ensures that both observed and unobserved confounders are equally distributed between the groups, allowing for a clean comparison of outcomes, and minimizing bias.

The conceptual model represented in *Figure 1* becomes:

Figure 2. RCT model.

As we can see in *Figure 2*, the randomization process attempts to break any linkage between the confounders. Since treatment assignment is randomized, the causal effect of the treatment on the outcome can be directly estimated by comparing outcomes between the treated and untreated groups, without having to condition the treatment on confounders. This is what allows RCTs to provide a strong basis for causal inference.

However, RCTs have also some limitations: they are often expensive and time-consuming, and not always feasible. This is where Machine Learning can help. In particular, we will study causality by means of a suitable machine learning model such as the Conditional Variational Autoencoder (CVAE).

3. Conditional Variational Autoencoder (CVAE)

Before diving into the functioning of a Conditional Variational Autoencoder, let's have first a brief overview of a standard Variational Autoencoder. A **Variational Autoencoder (VAE)** is a generative model: it generates new samples that resemble the original data. These "fake" samples should ideally be indistinguishable from real samples drawn from the underlying data distribution.

A VAE can be seen as an extension of an autoencoder, which is a neural network architecture designed to encode data into a lower-dimensional space and then decode it back to its original form. The primary goal of an autoencoder is to learn a compact representation of the data and be able to reconstruct the original data from this representation. Instead of learning a fixed encoding for each data point, the VAE learns a distribution, typically Gaussian.

Diving more into details, a VAE is made of two components:

- **Encoder:** it takes data as input and maps it to a probability distribution in a latent space, which captures the essential features and structures of the data. Specifically, the encoder outputs parameters (mean and variance) of this distribution.
- **Decoder:** it takes a point sampled from the latent distribution as input and maps it back to the original data space. If the VAE is trained well, this reconstructed data should closely resemble the original input.

The VAE is trained to minimize the two components of its loss function:

- **Reconstruction Loss (Mean Square Error):** it measures how well the decoded data matches the original input.
- **Regularization Term (Kullback-Leibler divergence):** it ensures that the probability distributions in the latent space are close to a standard normal distribution. This encourages the latent space to have a smooth and continuous structure, which is crucial for generating diverse and meaningful new samples.

A **Conditional Variational Autoencoder (CVAE)** is, again, an extension of the standard Variational Autoencoder (VAE). The primary distinction is that the CVAE conditions the generation process on additional information, making it a controlled generation process.

- **In the encoder:** along with the data, the encoder also receives label information as input. This allows the encoder to produce a probability distribution in the latent space that's influenced by the provided label.
- **In the decoder:** the decoder, in addition to the sampled point from the latent space, also receives the label information. This conditions the reconstruction on the label, ensuring that the output is tailored to the specific condition.

Because of its conditioning nature, CVAEs are particularly useful for controlled data generation.

Figure 3. Conditional Variational Autoencoder

4. The International Stroke Trial (IST) dataset

The goal of this section is to finally apply the Conditional Variational Autoencoder model to a real-world dataset, in order to study its functioning and explore the potential insights and benefits we can derive from its implementation.

The International Stroke Trial (IST) is a large randomized clinical trial that aims to determine the effectiveness of aspirin and heparin in the treatment of acute ischemic stroke.[2]

The primary goal of the IST was to understand if giving aspirin, heparin, both, or neither could influence the clinical course of acute ischemic stroke. The primary outcomes were death within 14 days and death or dependency at 6 months. In this report, we only focus on the 6-month outcome.

The Randomized Controlled Trial and results

In the IST, the researchers used an RCT method. This means that patients were randomly chosen to either receive the treatment or not. Each patient had an equal chance ($p=0.5$) of getting the treatment or being in the control group (not getting the treatment).

Among the patients who were administered aspirin, 62.2% were found to be either dead or dependent after 6 months. In comparison, 63.5% of the patients who did not take aspirin were either dead or dependent after the same duration. For the group of patients who were given heparin, 62.9% were categorized as either dead or dependent after 6 months. The same percentage (62.9%) of patients who did not receive heparin were also either dead or dependent at the 6-month checkpoint.

These results suggest that neither aspirin or heparin had a significant impact on the outcomes of these patients.

Factual and counterfactual data

We want to apply the previous CVAE model to the IST dataset and see whether results are consistent with the ones obtained with the RCT.

First of all, we need to briefly explain what factual and counterfactual data is:

Factual Data: they refer to the observed outcomes based on the actual interventions or treatments that were applied. In a clinical trial where half of the participants receive a new drug and the other half receive a placebo, the outcomes of each group after the treatment are the factual data. We can directly observe and measure these outcomes.

Counterfactual Data: they refer to the hypothetical outcomes that would have occurred if a different intervention or treatment had been applied, given everything else remained the same. Continuing with the clinical trial example, while we know the health outcomes of participants who received the new drug (factual data for that group), we don't know what would have happened to

those same participants if they had received the placebo instead. Their outcomes under the placebo scenario are the counterfactual data for that group.

At the heart of causal inference is the comparison of factual and counterfactual outcomes. However, a fundamental problem is that we can never observe both factual and counterfactual outcomes for the same participant at the same time. For instance, in the clinical trial example, a participant can either receive the drug or the placebo, but not both. We can't observe the same participant's outcomes under both scenarios simultaneously.

Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) address this problem by randomizing treatment assignment, ensuring that the treatment and control groups are comparable on average. This allows researchers to estimate average causal effects by comparing the factual outcomes of the two groups. However, the RCTs suffers the limitations we explained in section 2.

The power of the CVAE

How could we, instead, use a CVAE?

First, we reconstruct the original (factual) data with the CVAE model. The input to the CVAE model will be the outcome y of the patients (dead, dependent, not recovered, recovered), conditioned on the patients' characteristics and treatment (which can be taken or not taken).

Let's recall that the "conditional" aspect of a CVAE allows to generate data samples based on specific conditions, such as whether a treatment was applied. By training a CVAE on observed (factual) data, we can then use it to generate counterfactual outcomes by changing the conditions. For example, for a patient who actually received a treatment, the CVAE can be used to predict what might have happened if they hadn't received the treatment (and vice versa).

Figure 4. CVAE applied to the IST dataset

This process allows us to rebuild our existing data and also make predictions about data we haven't observed. Then, researchers can estimate the Individualized Treatment Effect (ITE) of the treatments for each patient.

Individual Treatment Effect (ITE): The ITE represents the difference in potential outcomes for a specific individual if they were to receive a treatment versus if they did not receive that treatment. Essentially, it quantifies the personalized effect of a treatment on an individual.

This means that the experts can make specific suggestions about when a treatment might be useful and identify particular groups of patients who are more or less likely to see benefits from the treatment.

5. Quality assurance and informed study

When we apply our model, we need to make sure that it is working properly. Ensuring the quality and reliability of a model, especially in medical applications, is crucial. That's why the first result deals with quality assurance: we need to quantify how accurate is the model, that is, how it is good in reproducing the same output as the original dataset. It is up to the user to decide the confidence level necessary to declare the model as reliable.

We represent **quality assurance** through a confusion matrix, such as:

Figure 5. Confusion matrix for quality assurance

Once the model is reliable, we can proceed with analyzing the results that our model provides. That is, we generate an **informed study** for the experts.

For example, we can show the **Individual Treatment Effect (ITE)** that was generated by our CVAE when studying heparin:

Figure 6. Individual Treatment Effect distribution

As explained in the previous section, the ITE represents the difference in potential outcomes for a specific individual if they were to receive a treatment versus if they did not receive that treatment.

$$\text{ITE} = P(\text{"death" or "no recovery" | treatment taken}) - P(\text{"death" or "no recovery" | treatment not taken})$$

If the ITE is *positive*, it suggests that the probability of the patient dying or not recovering is higher when they take the treatment compared to when they don't. In this scenario, for that particular patient, the treatment would be considered *harmful*. If the ITE is *negative*, it implies that the patient has a higher chance of survival or recovery when taking treatment compared to when they do not take it. Thus, for that individual, the treatment would be seen as *beneficial*.

In *Figure 6*, we notice that the ITEs distribution has mean around 0. This suggests that, on average, taking or not taking the treatment doesn't have a significantly different outcome. Given the mean ITE is 0, we can deduct that also the ATE would indicate no significant difference in outcomes between those who received the treatment and those who did not receive it.

Another important aspect that we can derive from the ITEs distribution is the **benefit effect size** and the **harm effect size**. The effect size essentially refers to the magnitude of the effect of a treatment. In fact, while the average treatment effect (ATE) might suggest a neutral or zero effect, analyzing the distribution of individual treatment effects (ITEs) can reveal crucial information about the heterogeneity of responses.

Figure 7. Benefit and harm effect size

For example, in Figure 7 here we can see that:

- **Benefit effect size:** The distribution suggests that the magnitude of any positive outcomes from the treatment isn't significantly different from outcomes observed when the treatment isn't administered.
- **Harm effect size:** Similarly, this distribution indicates that any adverse effects or negative outcomes from the treatment aren't significantly worse than the outcomes from not receiving the treatment.

In this specific case, the conclusion would be that there is “uniformly no effect” in taking or not taking the treatment. However, let’s recall that this conclusion would refer to the average: some individuals might experience substantial benefits, while others might experience very bad effects.

By analyzing the tails of the distribution of ITEs, one can identify subgroups of patients who are most likely to benefit (or be harmed) by the treatment. This can help in tailoring interventions and ensuring that treatments are only given to those who stand to benefit the most, minimizing risks.

Knowing the size of both the potential benefits and harms can guide clinicians and patients in making informed decisions. For instance, if a treatment offers a significant benefit for a subgroup but represents a risk for another, having this knowledge can help in weighing the risks against the benefits.

6. Framework: Generative Models in Artificial Intelligence

The CVAE model applied to the IST dataset is currently part of a more complex framework which deals with Machine Learning for causal inference in healthcare. This framework, which is still under development, also includes two other machine learning models:

- **CGAN (Conditional Generative Adversarial Network)**: a neural network model that uses a generative and discriminative network to generate data samples conditioned on specific attributes.
- **CAAE (Conditional Adversarial Autoencoder)**: a hybrid model that integrates the concepts of autoencoders and generative adversarial networks to generate data samples with control over attributes or conditions through an adversarial training process.

Additionally, a “**A Walkthrough of Generative models AI Framework**” notebook was designed, to provide users with a comprehensive and intuitive interface for engaging with generative models, specifically the Conditional Variational Autoencoder. The notebook guides the user through setting the configuration files, data configuration, resampling configuration, and finally applying the desired model to the dataset and plotting the result.

At the moment, the public repository only contains the CVAE model and a toy dataset, since the more complex scenario involving the whole framework is still under study.

The public repository can be found at:

<https://github.com/maximilian-janisch/generative-models/tree/main>

7. Conclusions

Machine learning possesses the remarkable potential to reshape healthcare research. Traditional methods, like Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs), though reliable, have their challenges, such as the need for many participants, meaning that they are not always feasible.

This is where machine learning models, such as the CVAE, step in. They offer a flexible way to dive deep into patient data. In fact, CVAEs can focus on the specific effects for each patient. Unlike RCTs, which typically yield average treatment effects, CVAEs can predict individual treatment effects, making them especially relevant for complex scenarios involving multimorbidity or multiple treatments. Furthermore, the nature of CVAEs, which allows for the prediction of probabilities based on observational data alone, presents a significant advantage.

Machine learning brings the unique capability of simulating scenarios that might be challenging, if not impossible, to achieve in real-world settings. However, it's not just about the data. The true value of these simulations is realized only when paired with the depth of expert knowledge. It is the experts who ensure the integrity of the data and provide context to the patterns emerging from it.

The collaboration between clinical researchers and machine learning is transformative. This partnership not only promises a more robust healthcare system but also equips experts with the tools to conduct richer, more insightful studies. The ultimate beneficiary of this synergy is the patient, who can expect improved care and outcomes.

8. References

[1] From single disease reductionist research to informed Machine Learning: a new research paradigm for multimorbidity - Pls: Prof. Andrea Burden, Prof. Alessio Figalli, Prof. Milo Puhon, Prof. Nicola Serra

[2] <https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1745-6215-12-101> "The International Stroke Trial database" - Peter AG Sandercock, Maciej Niewada, Anna Członkowska and for the International Stroke Trial Collaborative Group

[3] "Exploring the International Stroke Trial: Analyzing Aspirin and Heparin Effects and Predicting Outcomes using CVAEs" Olivia Jullian Parra (CERN), Sara Zoccheddu (CERN)

[4] "Progress on framework for Generative models in AI" - Maximilian Janisch, Olivia Jullian Parra, Shrija Sheth, Thomas Lehericy, Sara Zoccheddu

[5] "Conditional VAE in Healthcare" LHCb presentation 08/2023 – Sara Zoccheddu (CERN)